

AUDIO - LINGUAL METHOD FOR DEVELOPING VOCABULARY AND LISTENING SKILLS IN A2 LEARNERS

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Annotation. *Audio-lingual learning is increasingly used to develop students' vocabulary and listening skills of A2 level learners. In our research work we explore how an audio-lingual method improves students' skills, incorporating various method approach such as classroom observation, student questionnaires, teacher interview and pre- test and post- test analysis. The study involved 12 fifth- grade students during a brief teaching period. The study demonstrate that the use of drilling, repetition and interactive activities significantly improved learners' vocabulary and speaking. However, there were some problems such as students losing attention and too much use of repetition.*

Keywords: *Audio-lingual method, vocabulary, listening, A2 level learners, drilling, repetition.*

Introduction

In recent years, developing vocabulary and listening skills is essential, especially for young learners at A2 level, most students face some difficulties in remembering new words and do not use their daily life situations. The Audio-lingual method (ALM) focuses on repetition, drills, listening and speaking skills through daily practice.

THEORETICAL AND EMPIRICAL BACKGROUND

In this research, we explore how the Audio-Lingual Method improves vocabulary and listening skills in teaching the topic of “feelings” to A2 level learners. Then, I came across articles, videos by several ways while studying ‘FEELING’ topic. I present their opinions and summary below. The first resource is student’s book under the title “Integrated Module of Teaching Foreign Languages “ (Part 1) written by Tursunova Gulchexra and Polvanova Maxzuna [Tursunova & Polvanova, 2018, p254] In this book, the Audio-Lingual Method by listening is explained as a way of teaching based on behaviorism and language structures. This method focuses on forming good language habits through repetition and drills. Students learn by repeating sentences and practicing tasks.

The next article “12 Ways to Help Students Identify Their Emotions” published on Edutopia highlights the importance of emotional literacy as a key component of Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) Emotional literacy refers to students’ ability to recognize, understand, label, and appropriately express their feelings. Research in education shows that these skills improve self-regulation, academic performance, and peer relationships. The article presents practical classroom strategies to help students develop emotional awareness. For younger learners, teachers are encouraged to build emotional vocabulary through tools such as emotion charts, storytelling, and role-playing [Edutopia, 2020].

The third source is a video that explains the Audio- Lingual Method or Army method in language learning. One of the main ideas in the video is that students can learn vocabulary very quickly through repetition. Students repeat words and sentences during the lesson, which helps them remember easily way. Furthermore, pronunciation is essential for learners, they listen carefully and repeat after the teacher, this way improves their listening and speaking skills. In addition, the video shows that language could be learned in realistic contexts such as dialogues and short conversations are based on everyday situations, so learners can use the language in real life with their feelings [Learn English Stepwise Progress, 2023]. The fourth source is another video about emotions and feelings in English from the Learn English Stepwise Progress channel. The video focuses on teaching a lot of vocabularies related to various emotional and physical states, such as happy, sad, angry, tired, and excited. It presents these words in a simple and clear way, which makes it easier for students to understand and remember them. This method is especially useful for beginners who need more practice to remember new vocabulary. Furthermore, the video includes a wide range of feelings, from basic emotions like “happy” and “sad” to more complex ones like “confident,” “curious,” and “heartbroken.” This helps learners express themselves more clearly in different situations. Moreover, another useful way is that the vocabulary is connected to real-life contexts. Learners can use these words in daily conversations, for instance, when they are talking about their mood or physical condition. This makes the learning process more practical and meaningful during their life. The video also creates a relaxed learning environment, where students can learn without pressure. Repetition and clear pronunciation models help build confidence in speaking in front of others [Learn English Stepwise Progress, 2023].

words. That is why, this kind of visual videos very useful and effective way to engage students. The fifth source is the Guess What! Grade 5 student’s book and workbook written by Susannah Reed with Kay Bentley also series editor: Lesley Koustaff and publisher is Cambridge University Press [Reed et al, unit 7, p 66-82,2016, 2021]. Unit 7, which focuses on the topic of Feelings. This unit is designed to help young learners understand the feelings and use vocabulary related to emotions such as “happy,” “sad,” “tired,” “hungry,” and “worried.” The materials include different types of activities like listening, matching, speaking, and reading tasks. One of the main rule of this unit is its use of visual support. Pictures of children showing different emotions and this help students easily understand the meaning of new words. The unit also connects language with real-life situations. Activities like “I feel...” or asking “Why is he/she feeling this way?” or “How do you feel today?” this kind of questions help students think and use the language actively with audio - lingual method like drilling, role play games such as <https://topqir.uz/>.

The Audio- Lingual method is based on behaviorist theory, where language learning is seen as habit formation through repetition and drilling [Tursunova & polvanova, 2018]. Furthermore, emotional vocabulary plays an significant role in communication [Edutopia,2020].

Teaching emotions helps students show their feelings better and improves social interaction. Also, visual materials, videos, interactive games and real- life situation dialogues are very important in language learning.

Research methodology

This study a mixed- method research design to explore how Audio- lingual method in improving vocabulary and listening skills among A2 level learners. Moreover, quantitative data is collected through pre- test and post- tests by combining statistical analysis with qualitative with observations, questionnaires and teacher interview. This helps to identify students' progress and their classroom behavior.

Participants and context

The participants were 12 students in a school where English is taught as a foreign language. Their English level was A2 based on their English book. Students practiced the topic through repetition, drills and listening and speaking activities to observe their progress.

Instructional design and Intervention

The experimental class was taught using the Audio- lingual method. Lessons focused on repetition, drilling, and listening practice to help students improve vocabulary and listening skills. In class, the teacher presented new vocabulary and students repeated them several times. Activities included repetition drills, substitution drills, and dialogue practice. Students also practiced pronunciation and listened carefully.

Data Collection instruments

OBSERVATION LIST : I selected three various classes of the one teacher to make an observation and fill three observation sheets by ChatGPT. The main purpose of the observation was that the teacher used my chosen Audio - lingual method on her lessons period.

INTERVIEW: My interview includes five questions for teacher to answer. This interview help to me find out the teacher's knowing and awareness of my chosen Audio - lingual method.

PRE- TEST: Before starting lesson with my target 5th grade learners, I need to know their background knowledge about the chosen topic in advance. Actually results of pre - test is very important to know their knowledge and compare to the results of post - test. So pre- test includes 10 questions assessing general knowledge of my students and questions are not difficult to find correct answers , these are related to tenses, adjectives , emotions.

POST - TEST: After conducting lesson with my A2 level students, I need to find out where my lesson is useful, productive or less productive. Therefore, the questions of post- test are connected to vocabulary of 'Feelings' and listening and speaking skills during the lesson. A)**QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS** is a research method that expressed in words. It is used to understand concepts, thoughts or experiences. It helps researchers explore a topic in depth by looking at opinions, feelings with interview or open- ended questions, observations described in words and literature reviews.

B) **QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS** is expressed in numbers and graphs. It is used to test or confirm theories assumptions. This type of research can be used to establish generalizable facts about a topic such as how much, how many, how often, when , where. Also, researchers often use surveys with closed- ended questions, test , observations recorded as numbers and tables.

C)**COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS** is a side- by- side comparison that systematically compares two or more things and contrast variables to see their

similarities and differences. It can be used in mean fields such as education, culture, science to make clear and meaningful comparisons.

RESEARCH TOOLS: WPS, Microsoft word, PDF, Excel, Cams canner, Canva, Cup Cut, Smartphone, Google, ChatGPT5, RAR.

DATA ANALYSIS

I analyzed the collected data step by step, based on the methods I used during my research. First of all, I started with the observation. While preparing the observation form, I used ChatGPT to help me organize and create useful structure. During the lesson, I observed students' behavior, participation, and their use of feelings vocabulary. I noticed that at the beginning, some students were shy and not very active, which made it a bit challenging to communicate with classmates and teacher. Next, I analyzed the pre-test results. I conducted the pre-test before teaching the lesson to understand students' background knowledge. After that, I looked at the student questionnaire. It showed that students enjoy learning through games, visuals, and group activities. However, some students mentioned that they find it hard to remember new words, which was a challenge for assessing their real learning progress. Second question result is very clear and the teacher's explanation was generally clear and easy to understand, which helped students follow the topic without major difficulties. 3)The lesson activities were engaging and enjoyable. A high number of students found them interesting, which means the lesson was not boring and kept students' attention. 4)In terms of learning outcomes, the majority of students reported that they gained new knowledge. This indicates that the lesson was not only interesting but also educational and useful. 5)The games and interactive tasks played an important role in making the lesson more dynamic and fun. Students clearly responded positively to these elements. 6.Student participation was also quite high, as many felt active during the lesson. All students participated positively and this is reflected in the diagram. Only a very small number of students gave negative or neutral responses. After that, I analyzed the interview with teachers, conducted on practicum day during the big break in the teachers' room. I also evaluated the lesson planning process. While creating the lesson plan, I used ChatGPT as a supportive tool. I also collected handouts and worksheets from Google, YouTube, and Pinterest. Furthermore, I analyzed the post-test results and compared them with the pre-test. The comparison showed clear improvement in students' performance. Still, a few students needed extra support with spelling and sentence structure, because of they do not understand some grammar structures .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this action research, I tried to understand how effective the Audio-Lingual Method is in teaching the topic of feelings. This experience was very useful for me because I could observe students' learning and improve my own teaching skills. At the beginning of the research plans, I noticed that many students had limited vocabulary and lack of confidence in speaking English. They were often shy and afraid of making mistakes. During the lesson, I used various activities such as pair work and interactive games. After preparing the resources, then I created 4 research plan questions. I gave a pre-test to check students' knowledge. The average score was 5.75. This result showed that students did not know many words about feelings and they had difficulty expressing themselves in English. 1. Mean Score

$$X(\text{pre}) = 69 / 12 = 5.75$$

$$X(\text{post}) = 92 / 12 = 7.66$$

The average scores are: Pre-test mean score: 5.75

Post-test mean score: 7.66

2. Gained Score

Gain score = Post – Pre

Gain score = 7.66 – 5.75

Gained Score = 1.91

3.Hake Gain Score (Normalized Gain)

Hake Gain = $(7.66 - 5.75) / (10 - 5.75)$

Hake Gain = $1.91 / 4.25 = 0.45$

(Maximum score = 10)

Hake Gain Score ≈ 0.45

During the lessons, I used different techniques such as repetition drills and simple speaking exercises. Students repeated words and sentences and it helped them remember vocabulary better. However, I also faced some difficulties. Some students lost their attention easily, and a few students could not follow the fast pace of drills. After the teaching process, I gave a post-test. The average score increased to 7.66. The gain score was 1.91, and the Hake gain score was 0.45. This shows that students improved and the method was helpful.

CONCLUSION

From this research, I learned that teaching methods should be chosen carefully. A teacher should be flexible and creative. I believe that Audio - lingual method is an effective approach that can significantly improve student's vocabulary, listening with repetition, drilling and communicative competence with classmates. However, teachers should use it carefully and combine it with other approaches to improve student's knowledge and more repetition may reduce students' motivation. While, the Audio-Lingual method is more beneficial for improving oral skills with vocabulary. As a result, it can create more productive and engaging learning environment.

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